

A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY OF DRUG NAMES USED IN THERAPEUTIC DISEASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article describes ways to use the basics of drug naming that are currently relevant. In addition to classical methods, the basics of modern methods are presented.

In modern medicine, medicines and medicines are rapidly expanding and being updated. Renewal of medicines and medicines contributes to the renewal and increase in terms in medicine. With the advent of new pharmaceuticals, the challenge for pharmacists is to help physicians and pharmacists (pharmacists) identify drug names and select the best ones. Medicinal plant materials (MPR) are widely used in medicine to obtain various drugs: infusions and decoctions, tinctures, extracts, total preparations, etc. Recently, the output of new types of products from VP has increased (briquettes, filter bags, powders, tablets, etc.). Currently, medicines are used in Russia, which are obtained from substances of synthetic, vegetable, animal, mineral origin.

Medicines are also obtained from blood, blood plasma, organs and tissues of humans and animals, antibiotics and drugs obtained by microbiological means are used. Approximately one third of all medicines approved for medical use are obtained from medicinal plant materials. The use of herbal products is primarily due to their high biological activity, complex effect on the patient's body and safety in the treatment of various chronic diseases or for prevention purposes [10]. To date, drugs are mainly classified according to 3 different bases.

First, the name of the drug for pharmacological effects. The name of the drug is based on how it affects the human body.

For example:

Analgin is an anesthetic;

Aspirin is an antipyretic drug;

Diuretin is a diuretic.

The second name of the drug. The drug is called what it is made of (plants, animals, fungi, microbes or other creatures).

For example:

Papaverine is an herbal remedy (because papaverine is a poppy);

Menthol - peppermint (because menta means peppermint);

Biomycin is a natural fungus (because Bio is a natural fungus, a fungus is a fungus).

Thirdly, the name of the chemical composition of Dorin. The name of a chemical is a chemical substance or compound.

For example:

Calcii chloride - calcium chloride;

Carbo activatum - activated carbon;

Ferro-ascorbic acid is iron ascorbic acid.

Exactly the same remedies as mentioned above are called simple remedies. There are also drug names that are more complex, i.e. some of the above justifications may be related to medicine.

For example:

Corvalol or valocardine means valerian heart medicine. The presence of the element cor, the heart word, is characteristic of the first, and the name Val-Valeriana is an addition to the second. Phenoxymethylpenicillin is a phenylene containing phenyl, oxygen and methyl. Here, penicillin is the antibiotic on the first basis, and the additives - phen-, -oxy-, -methyl- are the names of the chemicals on the third basis.

A drug is a drug in a specific dosage form. Phytopreparation is a medicinal product of plant origin in a specific dosage form. Galenic drug is a herbal medicine in the form of a tincture or extract. Procurement of medicinal plant materials Biologically active substances of plants are contained in varying amounts in all parts of the plant body. However, to the greatest extent, they can accumulate selectively in certain parts: roots, stems (or their modifications - rhizomes), leaves, fruits, seeds, flowers. Therefore, it is advisable to harvest these particular parts of plants.

Each manufacturer must know:

- what to harvest (what plant, its signs, what parts)
- when to harvest (season, time of day)
- where to harvest (habitat, specially designated area)
- what and how to harvest (harvesting technique)

The buds are harvested in winter or early spring, when they are swollen, but have not yet begun to grow. This usually happens in March-April. By the beginning of the greening of the bud tops (birch, poplar), the collection is stopped, since the blossoming buds do not represent medicinal value. For medical purposes, birch, poplar, and pine buds are often used. Birch buds are harvested along with branches, starting in February. The branches are cut off, tied into small brooms, dried in the open air, threshed and cleaned of impurities [1-9].

If the kidneys are harvested during sap flow, then they are cut off by hand or immediately threshed. The buds of black poplar, aspen are cut off by hand, trying not to crush. Pine "buds" are harvested from young trees. Cut off the tops of the shoots and cut off the "buds" from them.

Dry the kidneys carefully: for a long time in a cool, ventilated room, as they begin to bloom in a warm room. The bark is collected only from young (not older than 3-4 years) stems, branches and shoots in early spring, during the period of increased sap flow and swelling of the kidneys. At this time, it is rich in healing substances and is easily separated due to the water-saturated layer of cambium, which separates the bark from the wood. Take off the smooth bark. Old, cracked bark contains a lot of cork tissue and few active ingredients. The bark is harvested from forest cuttings. From growing plants, the collection of this raw material is prohibited, as this leads to the formation of dead wood.

To remove the bark on the stem or shoot, make two semi-annular cuts with a sharp knife at a distance of 30-40 cm from one another and connect them together with two longitudinal cuts. The resulting bark grooves are separated from the wood. When collecting the bark, areas affected by lichens, with the remains of wood, darkened on the inside, fall [2-4]. It should be noted that when collecting this raw material, one can easily make a mistake in the species of the plant, since the bark is removed in the absence of leaves. Therefore, it is necessary to know the external signs of this plant well. Leaves. The collection of leaves is usually carried out during the period of budding and flowering of the plant. They do this in dry weather, plucking the leaves with their hands from top to bottom, with or without petioles.

It must be borne in mind that thick and juicy petioles slow down the drying of the leaves. In addition, they contain few medicinal substances. Only developed low and medium leaves are collected, and faded, fading, affected by insects or fungi are discarded. Juicy leaves (coltsfoot, purple foxglove, etc.) are folded loosely and quickly delivered to the place of drying. When harvesting nettle leaves, the plants are first mowed, and when the leaves are withered (lose their pungency), they are cut off.

You can dry the grass, and then thresh the leaves. 9 Wintering small leathery leaves (bearberry, lingonberry) are harvested in spring before flowering or in autumn after the berries ripen. Grass, that is, the above-ground part of plants, is cut or mowed at the level of the lower leaves. In some tall plants (wormwood, St. John's wort, motherwort, etc.), only leafy and flowering tops 15-20 cm long and side branches are cut. The thick, rough, woody stems contain few medicinal substances, so it is impractical to collect them. If the harvested plant has many stems (thyme, sweet clover, oregano), they are dried whole, and then the leaves from the stems are threshed. When collecting herbs, you can not pull out the plant along with the root (the exception is cudweed). Flowers and inflorescences are collected at the beginning of the flowering of plants, when they do not yet have signs of wilting. At this time, they contain many active ingredients, withstand drying, retain their color and crumble less during storage and processing.

Flowers and inflorescences are harvested by hand, plucking them and breaking off the pedicels, cutting them with scissors or secateurs (from trees). Inflorescences (baskets of chamomile, calendula, etc.) are collected in the phase of the horizontal arrangement of reed petals, and those plants that have only tubular flowers (tansy, odorous chamomile, etc.) - at the beginning of blooming marginal flowers. Overripe inflorescences crumble when harvested. Flowers are the most delicate part of the plant, so they are folded in a loose, thin layer, preferably in a wicker basket, trying not to crumple and protecting from direct sunlight. Novogalenic preparations are extracts from ballast substances, maximally purified from

ballast substances, containing in their composition the entire complex of biologically active substances. Tinctures - alcohol or water-alcohol extracts from herbs, obtained by various methods of infusion of raw materials with solvents without heating and removing the solvent.

Extracts are concentrated extracts from plant materials. According to the consistency they distinguish: liquid, thick (moisture not more than 25%), dry extracts - moisture not more than 5%. Solvents are - water, alcohol of various concentrations, ether, fatty oils, etc. Infusions and decoctions of herbal extracts, which differ in the time of infusion in a boiling water bath: 15 min. (infusions) and 30 min. (broths). Standardization of medicinal products - the establishment of authenticity, quality and other indicators in accordance with the requirements of the standard.

A standard is a normative document for general and reusable use that establishes rules, requirements, general principles or characteristics for achieving an optimal level of order in a particular area. A regulatory document is a document that establishes rules, general principles or characteristics of human activity or the results of this activity. There are also new types of drugs that differ from the classical principles described above. Therefore, these foundations have been called the modern method.

In addition to Latin (Greek) words, these medicines also contain parts of the English (German, French, Spanish, Russian, Polish, etc.) meanings. These modern names, in turn, give rise to many causes. For example, modern medicines may indicate which disease is used first. The emphasis here is on the use of expressive, emotional expressions common in world languages.

For example:

Bronchosan - ranch - bronx and san means for treatment;

GrippHot means flu and hot English fever;

Stoptussin are stops used in international traffic signs and tussi means tree;

Nolkoff is a sign with zero math, it is made from kof (English cough).

Modern pharmaceuticals under the second name can be found in the name of a pharmaceutical company or company.

For example: Ferrum Lec-Lec-Slack means an iron-based medicine; Upsarin Upsa means painkillers and fever made in the USA (Germany); ThromboPol is a drug used by Polpharma (Poland) for the treatment of vascular thrombosis. It is also desirable to highlight the third type of drug at the present stage, which does not contain information about the pharmacological properties of the drug.

However, names that are easy to remember are used as trademarks. For example: Enap is a modern version of enaprisin, a drug already in use.

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